

Vision & Goals

IDERHA (Integration of heterogenous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance) is a pioneering project addressing the obstacles in accessing, integrating and analysing health data to maximize their value for patient care and medical research.

To achieve this, IDERHA aims to create a scalable platform for the seamless integration of diverse health data. The aim is to support healthcare professionals, patients, and researchers with new capabilities to improve patient outcomes.

In addition, to ensure that patients and healthcare providers benefit from IDERHA's novel health solutions, the project seeks to accelerate policy development, regulatory approval and Health Technology Assessment (HTA).

Since IDERHA is building one of the first pan-European health data spaces, the project is strongly aligned with the implementation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

Patient Perspective

IDERHA strongly values the patient perspective in the work within the project and integrates this through the Patient Advisory Board (PAB), consisting of 10-15 people with experience with lung cancer or comparable diseases. IDERHA considers the PAB an invaluable asset for meaningful patient involvement and input throughout the project.

Partners

The IDERHA consortium consists of 33 partners coming from academia, clinical, medtech, pharmaceutical, IT and patient advocacy organisations as well as public authorities from across the EU and the world. IDERHA is led by the Fraunhofer Institute for Translational Medicine and Pharmacology ITMP and Johnson & Johnson GmbH, part of Johnson & Johnson MedTech.

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